

Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS): A Teaching Strategy to Improve Mastery Level in Subject-Verb Agreement Rules of Grade 10 Learners at General Luna National High School

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LEADS, Subject-Verb Agreement Rules, Mastery level, Grammatical competence, MELCs, teaching strategy

Abstract. The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS) a teaching strategy in improving mastery of subject-verb agreement rules. The researcher utilized a quantitative research approach with a quasi-experimental design. The study's respondents were 43 Grade 10 Learners from General Luna National High School, General Luna, Quezon. The researcher administered validated self-developed assessments and employed descriptive statistics, including mean, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage, as well as the T-test, to analyze the gathered data. The findings of the study revealed that the overall performance of the learners in the pretest was low, with a mean score of 11.12%. The result indicated that most grade 10 learners were underdeveloped in the mastery of subject-verb agreement rules. In contrast, the learners achieved the passing score in the posttest with a mean rating of 18.37%. It indicates that among 43 respondents, 95.4% demonstrated a high understanding of the rules of subject-verb agreement, indicating proficiency overall. When the pretest and posttest scores were compared, the results revealed a significant difference in the mastery of subject-verb agreement rules among grade 10 learners when the LEADS teaching strategy is used. The p-value was 0.0001, it was less than 0.05, indicating significance. The result connotes that implementing the LEADS strategy increases learners' grammatical awareness and improves grammatical competence, especially in mastering the rules of subject-verb agreement. Based on the findings of the study, an instructional material in the form of a module was proposed to maintain grammatical competence, specifically in the rules of subject-verb agreement.

Introduction

Language teaching plays a pivotal role in developing a child's writing ability. Basic grammatical competence taught in early childhood serves as the foundation for good writing skills. A strong foundation in grammatical competence supports learners' language acquisition, improves academic performance in all subject areas, and prepares them for future professional communication.

The implementation of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) significantly changes the language teaching and learning process. As an important component of grammar competence, learning grammar involves not only focusing on the rules but also applying them to achieve communication fluency. To acquire new grammar competence, teachers should use different methods when learners infer the meaning of specific structures and life-related situations (Pavlovych, 2017).

Despite many language-teaching approaches, learners still make language use errors, particularly in grammar. The study by Pandapatan (2020), titled *Analysis of the Subject-Verb Agreement Ability among Indonesian English Major Students as EFL Learners*, reveals that the majority of students commit errors in selecting the correct verb that agrees with the subject. This finding implies interference from the first language; using a second language to master subject-verb agreement leads

to struggle and confusion among learners. The study suggests that participants lacked sufficient knowledge to produce a well-written output.

In the Philippine context, proficiency in English is a prerequisite for all jobs, and speaking the language offers a wealth of opportunities. Cabaltica and Osabel (2021, as cited in Senobio, 2015) state that few pupils exhibit difficulties despite using the language since elementary school; they lack proficiency in speaking and writing. One factor contributing to this problem is their poor grammar skills.

In Addition, according to Hernandez (2023), Philippine English has been recognized as a linguistic issue in the Philippines. Although it has been the focus of numerous studies, many aspects remain under-researched. One such area is its grammatical characteristics, specifically subject-verb agreement. This aspect, particularly within academic contexts, has often been neglected in studies of Philippine English.

In 2020, during the pandemic, modular distance learning was implemented, and some intervention programs were provided to struggling learners at the General Luna National High School. Based on the diagnostic grammar test conducted by the teachers, 35 out of 200 (18%) students experienced difficulty with the use of linking verbs, subject-verb agreement, and verb tenses (Maaño, 2020).

Based on the aforementioned scenarios, the researcher conducted a study on the effectiveness of Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS) in improving mastery of subject-verb agreement rules among Grade 10 learners at General Luna National High School.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS) in improving mastery of subject-verb agreement rules among Grade 10 learners at General Luna National High School, General Luna District, Division of Quezon. Specifically, this research aimed to answer the following specific questions:

1. What is the mastery level in subject-verb agreement rules among Grade 10 respondents before implementing the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions?
2. What is the mastery level in subject-verb agreement rules among Grade 10 respondents after implementing the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions?
3. Is there a significant difference in the mastery level in subject-verb agreement rules among Grade 10 respondents before and after implementing the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions strategy?
4. What instructional materials in a form of module can be made by the researcher regarding the implementation and optimization of the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions strategy?

Methodology

Research Design

To investigate the effects of the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS) teaching strategy on students' mastery of subject-verb agreement, this study utilized a quantitative, quasi-experimental design.

This research design is crucial in determining the effectiveness of teaching strategies, as it allows researchers to establish cause-and-effect relationships through experimental conditions and systematic manipulation of variables. According to Garton, Ratti, and Giudice (2020), experimental research provides a structured approach by utilizing comparison and experimental groups, ensuring that observed changes are directly attributable to the grammar-teaching program rather than external factors. To determine the baseline mastery level of grade 10 learners in subject-verb agreement, a pretest was administered before the implementation of the LEADS teaching strategy. Additionally, the posttest was administered to grade 10 learners of General Luna National High School to investigate the effects of LEADS on the learners' mastery level.

This research design fits this study by employing a pretest-posttest design and statistical analysis. The study could generate empirical evidence on the effectiveness of LEADS by improving respondents' proficiency in subject-verb agreement and contributing valuable insights into language education practices.

Respondents/Participants

The population of this study came from Grade 10 learners of General Luna National High School, municipality of General Luna District under the Schools Division Office of Quezon Province. Grade 10 learners from section Bonifacio served as the experimental group for the implementation of the LEADS teaching strategy. Purposive sampling was employed in this study. This section consisted of 43 learners as the main population of the study, who were identified their mastery of subject-verb agreement after the pretest. Based on the results, 36 were at the beginning stage, 5 were at the developing stage, and 2 were at the proficient and advanced levels.

Instrument of the Study

To accomplish the study's objective, the researcher used a 20-item self-developed assessment aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs) of grade 10, Observe correct grammar in making definitions, with curriculum code EN10G-IIa-29. In Addition, the researcher used the DepEd learners Packet (LEAP) as basis for contextualizing learning material for grammar-teaching strategy. The researcher contextualized a learning aid. It contained the rules of subject-verb agreement, examples, activities, and a formative assessment to help the study respondents learn and assess their knowledge.

Moreover, the developed subject-verb agreement assessment used as research instrument was validated by the language master teachers from the Division of Quezon. The researcher sought suggestions and recommendations from selected experts. These research instruments underwent content and face validation. Then, the edited subject-verb agreement assessment was piloted in the other secondary public school in General Luna District, the San Isidro National High School, with 30 respondents for the reliability test (Bujang et al., 2024). Cronbach's Alpha was used to assess the instrument's reliability during pilot testing, ensuring internal consistency before full-scale implementation. The subject-verb agreement assessment was adjusted and finalized before its implementation to the Grade 10 Bonifacio of General Luna National High School, the subject of the study.

Procedure

The researcher presented a request letter to conduct the study. The research adviser and the Dean of the graduate school signed this letter. This letter was forwarded to the school's division superintendent for due consent and forwarded to the public schools district supervisor for the appropriate approval. The signed letter was then attached to the validated subject-verb agreement assessment and distributed to the school head of General Luna National High School for data collection. In Addition, a cover was attached to the validated subject-verb agreement assessment, ensuring the respondent's privacy and confidentiality of the information provided. Upon approval of the communication from the Department of Education (DepEd) personnel.

Thereafter, the pretest was administered on September 18, 2025, to the Grade 10 Bonifacio students to determine their level of mastery in subject-verb agreement. The researcher ensured that each student answered independently and was in a comfortable environment, minimizing reliance on peers.

After determining the learners' mastery level, the researcher implemented the LEADS intervention from October 16 to December 3, 2025. Each session is conducted from 3:15 PM to 4:00 PM. The session includes review of the past lesson, a pre-activity to introduce the upcoming rules, followed by a focused discussion of four subject-verb agreement rules in each session, and a formative assessment designed to evaluate whether the learners have achieved mastery of the specific rules covered during that session.

To assess the effectiveness of the LEADS teaching strategy, a posttest was conducted on December 9, 2025 after various sessions. The posttest utilized the same set of questions as the pretest; however, the items were rearranged to maintain validity while reducing recall bias. The data gathered from the respondents were tallied, statistically treated, analyzed, and interpreted.

Data Analysis

The data gathered in this study were systematically collected, organized, analyzed, and interpreted in collaboration with the designated statistician, using appropriate statistical techniques.

For statements of the problem one (1) and two (2), the mastery level of subject-verb agreement rules among grade 10 learners before and after the grammar teaching program, this research used descriptive statistics such as mean for

determining the average mastery level of students from two (2) sections, standard deviation to measure the dispersion of scores from the mean, and frequency and percentage to classify students based on the mastery levels.

For statement of the problem number three (3), the significant difference in mastery level in subject-verb agreement rules among Grade 10 learners, a Paired-Sample t-test (Dependent t-test) was applied to compare the pretest and posttest scores of Grade 10 Bonifacio learners. This test assessed whether the LEADS teaching strategy significantly improved students' mastery of subject-verb agreement rules. Since only students from Section Bonifacio were included in the teaching strategy.

Key Features and Description of Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS)

Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS) is a teaching strategy designed to enhance Grade 10 learners' mastery of subject-verb agreement rules. The key feature of LEADS is the implementation of limited and focused discussions on subject-verb agreement rules per session, supported by printed learning materials that learners can access anytime to reinforce their understanding and retention of concepts. Each session's learning material is systematically structured to include a review of the previous lesson, a pre-activity that introduces the new topic, and a focused discussion of four specific rules per session. Furthermore, each session concludes with a formative assessment designed to evaluate whether the learners have successfully achieved mastery of the targeted rules. Another key feature of LEADS is its use of flexible time. In cases where a student is absent during a session, the learner is still provided with the corresponding learning material. This allows the teacher to deliver the missed lesson at any convenient time and in any suitable setting. Through this approach, students are given equal opportunities to catch up and achieve mastery of the targeted subject-verb agreement rules despite their absence.

Ethical Considerations

This study involved Grade 10 learners as respondents, and ethical considerations were carefully addressed. The research adhered to the principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice (Drewry, 2024, as cited in National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979).

The researcher obtained full consent from the respondents through an Informed Consent Form (ICF) to ensure their respect. The ICF was also attached to the research instrument to ensure that participants were properly informed before answering. Following this process, formal approval from the school principal was secured, and consent letters were provided to the subject teachers and advisers to notify them of the study. The respondents were notified that their participation was scheduled from September 18, 2025, to December 9, 2025, from 3:15 to 4:00 pm at General Luna National High School.

The researcher upheld the principle of beneficence by ensuring that participation in the study posed no physical, psychological, or academic risks. They were informed that their participation in the teaching strategy, Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS), is completely voluntary; this is designed to support student learning without causing undue stress or pressure, and they may refuse to join or withdraw at any time without any penalty or negative effect on their grades or standing in school (Magbanua, 2024, as cited in Obenza et al., 2024).

To promote justice, confidentiality, and data protection, all respondents were treated fairly and equitably, with no bias in selection based on academic performance, gender, or socio-economic background. In Addition, the information collected from this study is strictly confidential. The researcher also ensured that the names or any personal details of respondents would not appear in any report, presentation, or publication resulting from this research. Instead, codes or numbers were used to protect their identity. The data gathered, such as test results and activity outputs, were only accessed by the researcher. After the study was completed, all records were securely deleted to ensure their privacy. This action means that everything shared or contributed during the study remained private and could only be used for academic and research purposes.

Results and Discussion

Part I. Mastery Level in Subject-Verb Agreement Rules Among Grade 10 Respondents Before Implementing the LEADS

Mastery Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Beginning (0-13)	28	65.12
Developing (14-15)	13	30.23
Proficient (16-17)	1	2.33
Advanced (18-20)	1	2.33
Total	43	100
Mean of Scores	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
11.12	2.46	Developing

Table 1. Mean Scores on the Mastery Level in Subject-Verb Agreement Rules Before Implementing the LEADS

Table 1 reveals the mastery level in subject-verb agreement rules among Grade 10 respondents before implementing the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions. Findings revealed that 65.12% (28) of grade 10 learners demonstrated a minimal understanding of the rules and obtained low pretest scores, indicating they were beginning at the mastery level in subject-verb agreement. Additionally, 30.23% (13) of grade 10 learners demonstrated a moderate level of knowledge, interpreted as developing toward the mastery level. In contrast, a small number of learners demonstrated a high level of mastery of subject-verb agreement rules, with 4.66% (2) at both proficient and advanced levels.

As reflected in the data, respondents' overall performance in the pretest was low, with a mean score of 11.12%. The result indicated that most grade 10 learners were underdeveloped in the mastery of subject-verb agreement rules.

This result is likewise evident in the study by the Philippines and Tan (2020), in which the pretest results before the strategy indicated a developing mastery stage. Similarly, Baronia's (2020) study, found that students had difficulty with subject-verb agreement because they could not correctly identify the appropriate verb in sentence construction. Likewise, Peña's (2021) study found that the learner had poor mastery of subject-verb agreement rules and their use in both spoken and written communication before the intervention. Consistent with the present findings, previous studies by Abeywickrama and Amaraweera (2023), Moslemi et al. (2023), Belarmino (2024), Abendan et al. (2024), and Magbanua (n.d.) collectively revealed that learners struggled and demonstrated low mastery of subject-verb agreement rules during the pretest. Thus, emphasizing the need for an effective teaching strategy focused on subject-verb agreement.

Part II. Mastery Level in Subject-Verb Agreement Rules among Grade 10 Respondents After Implementing the LEADS

Mastery Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Beginning (0-13)	0	0
Developing (14-15)	2	4.7
Proficient (16-17)	10	23.3
Advanced (18-20)	31	72.1
Total	43	100
Mean of Scores	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
18.37	1.41	Proficient

Table 2. Mean Scores on the Mastery Level in Subject-Verb Agreement After Implementing the LEADS

Table 2 presents the mastery level in subject-verb agreement rules among grade 10 respondents after implementing the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions. This result reveals that after conducting LEADS, 72.1% (31) of the grade 10 learners achieved a high score on the posttest, indicating advanced mastery of subject-verb agreement. Relatively similar: 23.3% (10) of the learners showed an increase in knowledge of the rules of subject-verb agreement, interpreted as proficient. However, there were still 4.7% (2) learners who displayed a minimal error in using the correct rules of subject-verb agreement, interpreted as developing. Notably, the result significantly improved, with no learners classified as beginning level.

The data showed that the learners achieved the passing score in the posttest with a mean rating of 18.37%. It indicates that among 43 respondents, 95.4% demonstrated a high understanding of the rules of subject-verb agreement, indicating proficiency overall. The findings revealed that implementing the LEADS teaching strategy improved mastery of subject-verb agreement rules among grade 10 learners.

The findings are in line with those of the Philippines and Tan (2020), who concluded that a proficient rating was the mean score of the participants after the English grammar proficiency intervention. Likewise, Peña (2021) reported the highest mean posttest score, further supporting the pretest result. Similarly, Baronia (2020) reported significant improvements in students' grammatical accuracy and overall writing skills following the implementation of the teaching method. However, a few learners remained at the developing level, which aligns with Belarmino's (2024) study. Following the intervention strategy, some learners attained a "fairly satisfactory" rating or successfully met the Department of Education's 75% criterion.

Part III. Test for Significant Difference in the Mastery Level in Subject-Verb Agreement Rules Among Grade 10 Respondents Before and After Implementing the LEADS

Pre-Test Mean	Post-Test Mean	Mean Difference	P- Value	Decision
11.12	18.37	7.26	<0.0001	With Significant Difference

Table 3. The Significant Difference in the Mastery Level in Subject-Verb Agreement Rules Before and After Implementing LEADS

Table 3 presents the data on the difference in pretest and posttest mastery levels in subject-verb agreement rules among grade 10 respondents before and after implementing the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions. The data revealed an increase in posttest scores, indicating that learners improved their mastery of subject-verb agreement rules after implementing the LEADS strategy. To test for differences between paired observations, a T-test was used. Given the statistical results, the p-value was less than 0.05, indicating significance. Based on the statistical results, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Results showed a significant difference in mastery of subject-verb agreement rules among grade 10 learners when the LEADS teaching strategy was used. The result connotes that implementing the LEADS strategy increases learners' grammatical awareness, especially in mastering subject-verb agreement.

The study findings are consistent with Peña (2021), who reported that the posttest mean was higher than the pretest mean, with the difference being statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This finding is further supported by Abendan et al. (2024), who reported a significant improvement from pretest to posttest in English learners' grammatical competence through the integration of structured interventions and engaging learning materials. It was likewise affirmed by Abeywickrama and Amaraweera (2023), Moslemi et al. (2023), Belarmino (2024), and Magbanua (n.d.) that there was a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores, which highlighted a significant improvement in the awareness of grammatical rules when incorporating an effective language teaching strategy with contextualized learning activities rather than traditional grammar instruction.

Grade 10 Bonifacio	Pretest Score	Posttest Score	Gain
Learner 1	11	18	7
Learner 2	9	15	6
Learner 3	11	19	8
Learner 4	9	17	8
Learner 5	10	15	5
Learner 6	10	18	8
Learner 7	10	18	8
Learner 8	9	16	7
Learner 9	10	17	7
Learner 10	13	17	4
Learner 11	10	17	7
Learner 12	14	17	3
Learner 13	9	20	11
Learner 14	10	20	10

Learner 15	15	20	5
Learner 16	14	18	4
Learner 17	10	16	6
Learner 18	12	17	5
Learner 19	9	17	8
Learner 20	13	18	5
Learner 21	12	19	7
Learner 22	10	19	9
Learner 23	10	19	9
Learner 24	14	19	5
Learner 25	11	18	7
Learner 26	7	20	13
Learner 27	12	20	8
Learner 28	8	17	9
Learner 29	9	19	10
Learner 30	12	19	7
Learner 31	14	18	4
Learner 32	11	19	8
Learner 33	17	20	3
Learner 34	11	20	9
Learner 35	12	20	8
Learner 36	12	18	6
Learner 37	8	20	12
Learner 38	10	19	19
Learner 39	10	20	10
Learner 40	10	19	9
Learner 41	10	19	9
Learner 42	10	19	9
Learner 43	20	20	0
	Mean Score	Mean Score	Mean Gain
	11.12	18.37	7.26

Table 4. Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Grade 10 Bonifacio as Experimental Group Before and After Implementing the LEADS

Table 4 presents the pretest and posttest scores of the Grade 10 Bonifacio students as the experimental group before and after implementing the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions. The analyzed data showed significant improvement in learners' performance in Language Orientation, Development, and Innovation.

Based on the data presented, Grade 10 Bonifacio learners demonstrated low to average knowledge of the subject-verb agreement rules after the pretest, with scores ranging from 9 to 14; only a limited number achieved a high score. This result shows that they have a limited mastery of subject-verb agreement rules before the teaching strategy.

The posttest scores of Grade 10 Bonifacio improved. The majority of learners scored between 17 and 20. This result indicates that most learners improved their knowledge after exposure to the LEADS.

Overall, Grade 10 Bonifacio learners demonstrated greater improvement from pretest to posttest. This significant improvement suggests that the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS) was effective in improving mastery of subject-verb agreement rule among Grade 10 Bonifacio learners.

These findings were similar to those of Cabaltica and Osabel (2021), who emphasized targeted reinforcement for students with weak foundational grammar skills through scaffolded learning activities and contextualized exercises to enhance their proficiency. Likewise, Rifiyanti et al. (2023) found that students performed better when grammar rules were taught through contextualized examples and interactive exercises rather than rote memorization.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary

The study aimed to determine the effectiveness of Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS) in improving mastery of subject-verb agreement rules among Grade 10 learners at General Luna National High School, General Luna District, Division of Quezon. Furthermore, it sought to determine the learners' mastery of subject-verb agreement rules before and after the LEADS teaching strategy. Also, the significant difference between pretest and posttest scores was analyzed. As a result, an instructional material in a form of module was developed as an output of this study. The study included 43 respondents from Grade 10, section Bonifacio. This study utilized a quantitative research approach with a quasi-experimental design, in which a teaching strategy was implemented and researcher-developed, validated assessments were administered. This research employed descriptive statistics, including the mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentage, and an independent t-test to analyze the collected data.

Summary of Findings

In light of the analyzed and presented data, this study obtained the following findings:

1. The learners obtained low pretest scores, indicating that most of them were at the developing level of mastery in subject-verb agreement.
2. Learners demonstrated a very high performance on the posttest compared to their pretest scores. This finding revealed a high understanding of the rules and was interpreted as proficient.
3. The p-value obtained from the test comparing pretest and posttest scores was less than 0.05. This result indicates a significant difference and leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The scores of Grade 10 Bonifacio significantly improved after the posttest. These results suggested that the LEADS teaching strategy was effective in improving grade 10 learners' mastery level of subject-verb-agreement rules.
4. In light of the findings, Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions is therefore an effective teaching strategy for improving learners' mastery of subject-verb agreement. Consequently, instructional material in a form of module was proposed and developed for production and classroom implementation.

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, the researcher concluded that the majority of learners demonstrated basic mastery of subject-verb agreement rules before the implementation of the Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions. However, a substantial proportion of learners demonstrated a strong understanding of subject-verb agreement rules, made occasional errors, and applied the rules correctly most of the time, as indicated by the posttest results. Additionally, there was a significant difference in mastery of subject-verb agreement rules among Grade 10 respondents before and after implementing the Language Enhancement through Active Developmental Sessions strategy, as indicated by the pretest and posttest scores; hence, the null hypothesis was rejected. Essentially, Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions (LEADS) strategy is an effective teaching strategy for improving learners' mastery of subject-verb agreement rules. Moreover, the Language Enhancement through Active Developmental Sessions strategy can be implemented with a flexible schedule, regardless of the learner's attendance irregularities. Also, students actively participated in discussion exchanges during LEADS, which effectively reinforced their understanding and mastery of subject-verb agreement rules. Thus, the instructional material in a form of module for LEADS was developed as a tool to guide learners in expanding their knowledge of subject-verb agreement rules.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, which revealed that Language Enhancement Through Active Developmental Sessions is effective in improving the mastery level of the learners in subject-verb agreement rules, the researcher hereby recommends the following:

1. For the Department of Education (DepEd) Officials. Findings revealed that the LEADS teaching strategy is effective in improving learners' mastery of subject-verb agreement; therefore, it is recommended that school administrators validate and implement it before using it in intervention classes to ensure its optimization accuracy, alignment with established rules of subject-verb agreement, and to enhance mastery among learners in need.

2. For School Heads. Based on the findings, the LEADS teaching strategy is effective when there is supplementary material that serves as a guiding tool for improving the learner's mastery of subject-verb agreement. Thus, it is recommended to allocate funds for the production of LEADS material as supplemental material in the conduct of teaching strategy. They may also provide training/workshops on implementing LEADS for subject-verb agreement. To strengthen this initiative, an action plan is recommended.

3. For Teachers. Findings indicated that teachers played an essential role in improving learners' mastery of subject-verb agreement rules. Therefore, it is suggested that they collaborate with their school head to actively participate in training sessions and mentoring programs regarding the implementation of LEADS. They may also suggest enhancement of the LEADS strategy by incorporating technology or gamification during implementation.

4. For Learners. Based on the study's findings, the LEADS teaching strategy is beneficial for learners, as it enhances grammatical competence, particularly in subject-verb agreement. However, some students recorded absences during LEADS. Therefore, learners are encouraged to participate actively and are provided with additional academic support to ensure that learning outcomes are still achieved despite personal circumstances.

5. For Parents. The findings proved that LEADS significantly improved the mastery level of subject-verb agreement rules among learners, the parental support is highly encouraged, as their involvement not only motivates learners but also strengthens the continuity of learning, particularly for those who need improvement in grammatical competence.

6. For Stakeholders. The findings showed that LEADS is an effective teaching strategy. Thus, strong partnership with stakeholders and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) is essential, as they play a vital role in funding education, especially when the school lacks funds. It is recommended to build strong connections with stakeholders, as they are also an essential part of the school's development and contribute effectively to the teaching and learning process.

7. For Future Researchers. Given the quantitative nature of this study, future researchers may undertake a qualitative study to gain a deeper understanding of the factors contributing to the level of mastery in subject-verb agreement rules within the district.

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Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

References

- Abendan, J. B., Briones, J. A., & Tecson, J. C. (2024). Grammatical competence of UM Digos College English language learners. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Multidisciplinary Education*, 3(4), 621–631. <https://doi.org/10.58806/ijirme.2024.v3i4n17>
- Abeywickrama, D. D., & Amaraweera, S. (2023). Exploring subject-verb agreement challenges in the writing of ESL learners: An action research study in Sri Lanka. *Proceedings of the SLIIT International Conference on Advancements in Sciences and Humanities*. <https://doi.org/10.54389/QNAD1556>
- Baronia, J. M. B. (2020). Enhancing the Sentence Construction Skills of Tvl Students Through Instruct, Integrate, Involve (3I'S) Method. *IOER International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 2(2), 46–51. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3615156>
- Belarmino, V. S. (2024). Strategic intervention materials on subject-verb agreement: A tool for the enhancement of students' grammatical competence. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(1), 160–173. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10553812>
- Bujang, M. A., Omar, E. D., Foo, D. H. P., & Hon, Y. K. (2024). Sample size determination for conducting a pilot study to assess reliability of a questionnaire. *Restorative dentistry & endodontics*, 49(1). <https://doi.org/10.5395/rde.2024.49.e1>
- Cabaltica, R. B., & Osabel, C. A. (2021). Knowledge on subject-verb agreement of Grade 7 students: Basis for remedial teaching. *European Journal of Humanities and Educational Advancements*, 2(4), 74–82. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4817495>
- Drewry, S. (2004). The ethics of human subjects' protection in research. *Journal of Baccalaureate Social*
- Garton, E. O., Ratti, J. T., & Giudice, J. H. (2020). Research and experimental design. In N. J. Silvy (Ed.), *The Wildlife Techniques Manual* (7th ed., Vol. 1). Johns Hopkins University Press. <https://doi.org/10.56021/9781421436708>
- Hernandez, H. P. (2023). Does Philippine English subject-verb agreement exist in academic writing? The case of research articles across disciplines. *Asian Englishes*, 26(2), 337–354. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13488678.2023.2222347>
- Maaño, S. (2020). *Language Orientation, Development and Intervention*. General Luna National High School, Division of Quezon. (Unpublished school record).
- Magbanua, J. J. (2024). Enhancing English grammar skills of Grade 9 students through the use of an English grammar application. *ELT Worldwide: Journal of English Language Teaching*, 11(2), 394–405. <https://doi.org/10.26858/eltww.v11i2.66180>
- Moslemi, Y., Abadikhah, S., & Yaqubi, B. (2023). The Effects of Immediate and Delayed Corrective Feedback on the Acquisition of English Subject-Verb Agreement by EFL Learners. *Journal of English Language Teaching and Learning*, 15(32), 197–214. https://elt.tabrizu.ac.ir/article_16872_06fab0bfaf9c73f7b62f6c0ff03894ec.pdf
- Pandapatan, A. M. (2020). Analysis of the subject-verb agreement ability among Indonesian English major students as EFL learners. *Journal of English Language Studies*, 5(2), 132–141. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ITSE-09-2020-0212>
- Pavlovych, A. V. (2017). *Communicative Approach in Grammar Teaching*.
- Peña, A. (2021). Addressing subject-verb agreement problems through interactive slides. *Asian Intellect for Academic Organization and Development Inc.*, 21(1), 19–22. <https://www.academia.edu/download/102161168/872833412e577e1c299a5a15353465c1.pdf#page=17>
- Philippines, E. C. H. C., & Tan, M. (2020). Effectiveness of using a flipped classroom in improving English grammar proficiency. *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)*, 51(2), 45–57.
- Rifiyanti, H. (2023). Subject verb agreement test outcome analysis. *BABASAL English Education Journal*, 4(1), 122. <https://lonsuit.unismhluwuk.ac.id/index.php/BEEJ/article/view/2867>

Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.